

Chemoenzymatic Transformation of the Natural Antitumour Alkaloid 20-*O*-Acetylcamptothecin to Mappicine Ketone and (*S*)-Mappicine^{†#}

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Microwave irradiation of the naturally occurring antitumour alkaloid 20-*O*-acetylcamptothecin affords *trans*- and *cis*- $\Delta^{19,20}$ -20-*O*-acetylmappicine and 17-acetylmappicine ketone. The first two products when treated with dilute alkali yield mappicine ketone, an antiviral lead compound, which is reduced with baker's yeast to form another natural alkaloid, (*S*)-mappicine. Baker's yeast treatment of the major product, *trans*- $\Delta^{19,20}$ -20-*O*-acetylmappicine produces both mappicine ketone as well as (*S*)-mappicine. The last compound is converted to mappicine ketone by oxidation with pyridinium chlorochromate.

Camptothecin (1)¹, a naturally occurring pyrrolo[3,4-*b*]quinoline alkaloid is well-known for its promising antitumour activity². It acts as an inhibitor of DNA topoisomerase I³. The compound was originally isolated¹ from the Chinese plant *Camptotheca acuminata* Decne (Nyssaceae). Indian *Nothapodytes foetida* (Wight) Sleumer [formerly, *Mappia foetida* Miers (Icacinaeae)] has been found⁴⁻⁶ to be a rich source of this compound. The Indian plant yielded another two antitumour alkaloids, 9-methoxycamptothecin (2)⁴⁻⁶ and 20-*O*-acetylcamptothecin (3)^{5,6}. The *E*-ring lactone of camptothecins has been proved⁷ to be the most critical structural feature with respect to their antitumour activity. The decarboxylated *E*-ring analogue of

- 1 R = R¹ = H
2 R = OMe, R¹ = H
3 R = H, R¹ = Ac

camptothecin, known as mappicine ketone (4)⁸⁻¹⁰ has also been isolated in low yield from *N. foetida*. The compound does not exhibit an antitumor activity. However, the compound has recently been identified¹¹ as an antiviral lead. It possesses significant activity against the herpesviruses (HSV-I and HSV-2) and human cytomegalovirus (HCMV). Mappicine ketone (4) is an oxidised form of (*S*)-mappicine (5)^{9,10,12}, another minor alkaloidal constituent of *N. foetida*. Synthesis and transformations of camptothecins as well as

of mappicine ketone and (*S*)-mappicine are challenging work in recent years. Previously we reported⁸⁻¹⁰ the conversion of camptothecin (1) and 9-methoxycamptothecin (2) to different bioactive natural alkaloids. In continuation of our work on campto-thecins we report here the chemoenzymatic transformation of 20-*O*-acetylcamptothecin (3) to both mappicine ketone (4) and (*S*)-mappicine (5).

Results and Discussion

20-*O*-Acetylcamptothecin (3) was irradiated under microwave irradiation for 7-min. Three products were formed. These were characterised as *trans*- $\Delta^{19,20}$ -20-*O*-acetyl-mappicine (6; yield 64%), *cis*- $\Delta^{19,20}$ -20-*O*-acetylmappicine (7; yield 22%) and 17-acetylmappicine ketone (8; yield 8%) (Scheme 1). The structures of the products were settled from spectral data (vide Experimental) as well as from molecular modeling. The ¹H nmr spectra of 6-8 are very similar in the aromatic region to that of camptothecin (1). It means that *A-D* rings of all the compounds are similar. The ¹H nmr spectrum of 6 showed the presence of three methyl groups at δ 2.36 (3H, s, Me-17), 2.22 (3H, s, OAc) and 1.79 (3H, d, *J* 7.0 Hz, Me-18) and of an olefinic proton at δ 5.63 (1H, q, *J* 7.0 Hz, H-19). In the *cis*-compound 7 the corresponding three methyl groups resonated in the ¹H nmr spectrum at δ 2.31 (3H, s, Me-17), 2.13 (3H, s, OAc) and 1.65 (3H, d, *J* 7.0 Hz, Me-18) and the olefinic proton at δ 5.67 (1H, q, *J* 7.0 Hz, H-19). The ¹H nmr spectra of both compounds 6 and 7 were verified by molecular modeling which clearly indicated the *trans*- and *cis*-configurations of the C-19-C-20 double bond of these two compounds respectively. Compound 8 contains two methyl groups which absorb in the ¹H nmr spectrum at δ 2.11 (3H, s, Ac-17) and 1.28 (3H, t, *J* 7.0 Hz, Me-18).

Recently we have reported⁸ the microwave irradiation of camptothecin (1) and 9-methoxycamptothecin (2) to produce the corresponding mappicine ketones. The formation

[†] The paper is dedicated respectfully to Professor Sukh Dev.

[#] Part 9 in the series 'Synthetic Studies on Natural Products'; for Part 8 see, B. Das and A. Kashinatham, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1998, submitted. IICT Communication no. 4108.

of the products may be explained by a mechanism involving the elimination of carbon dioxide from the *E*-ring followed by 1,5-hydrogen shift from OH group to C-17 (Scheme 2).

Camptothecin (1) and 9-methoxycamptothecin (2) contain an α -hydroxylactone. In 20-*O*-acetylcampthoecin an acetoxy group is present at C-20. However, the forma-

tion of products 6 and 7 by irradiation of compound 3 may be explained (Scheme 3) by a similar mechanism as shown above but the 1,5-hydrogen migration occurs from the position 19 to C-17.

The compound 8 is probably formed by the migration of the acetyl group from the acetoxy group at C-20 to C-17 (Scheme 4).

Scheme 4

Compounds **6** and **7** when separately treated with 10% potassium hydroxide solution in methanol, afforded mappicine ketone (**4**)⁸ in excellent yield. The structure of the product was settled from its physical and spectral properties as well as by direct comparison with an authentic sample. As the two compounds **6** and **7** are the major constituents (86%) of the reaction products of the microwave irradiation of 20-*O*-acetylcamptothecin (**3**) the method described here is efficient and convenient for the conversion of the natural alkaloid **3** to the antiviral lead compound **4**. The last compound was treated⁹ with baker's yeast which is frequently used for stereospecific reduction of carbonyl compounds. The product was identified here as the naturally occurring (*S*)-mappicine (**5**)^{9,10}; ee 85% from its physical and spectroscopic data and by direct comparison with an authentic sample. Compound **5** was oxidised with pyridinium chlorochromate to produce mappicine ketone (**4**).

The major product (**6**) of the microwave irradiation of **3** was also treated with baker's yeast. Both the compounds, mappicine ketone (**4**) and (*S*)-mappicine (**5**) were produced. The acetoxy group at C-20 of **6** was at first hydrolysed by baker's yeast to form mappicine ketone (**4**) which was subsequently reduced to (*S*)-mappicine (**5**); ee 85%.

To summarize, the naturally occurring alkaloid, 20-*O*-acetylcamptothecin has been converted for the first time to mappicine ketone, an antiviral lead compound and its natural reduction product, (*S*)-mappicine by a simple and efficient chemoenzymatic method involving the microwave irradiation of the parent alkaloid followed by alkaline hydrolysis and baker's yeast treatment of the major products.

Experimental

Melting points were determined on a Buchi-510 instrument and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Nicolet 740 spectrophotometer, ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectra on a Varian Gemini 200 MHz spectrometer and mass spectra on a VG micromass 7070H (70 eV) instrument. Optical rotations were measured with a Jasco DIP 360 polarimeter. Column chromatography was performed on silica gel (BDH, 100–200 mesh) and tlc using silica gel GF-254. Tlc spots were detected under uv-light and in an iodine chamber.

Microwave irradiation of 20-*O*-acetylcamptothecin (3) : 20-*O*-Acetylcamptothecin (**3**; 500 mg) was taken in an

Erlenmeyer flask and placed in an alumina bath inside a commercial microwave oven (BPL BMO 700T). The compound was irradiated at full power (466 W) for 7 min. The reaction mixture was taken out from the oven and was cooled to the room temperature. The mixture was shaken with CH₂Cl₂ (30 ml) and filtered. The filtrate was concentrated. The major reaction product, *trans*-Δ^{19,20}-20-*O*-acetylmappicine (**6**) crystallised out (264 mg) and was separated by filtration. The concentrated filtrate was purified by column chromatography, the column being eluted with solvents of increasing polarity using hexane, EtOAc and MeOH. The fractions eluted with 40% EtOAc in hexane afforded some more *trans*-Δ^{19,20}-20-*O*-acetylmappicine (**6**; 37 mg). *Cis*-Δ^{19,20}-20-*O*-acetylmappicine (**7**; 104 mg) and 17-acetylmappicine ketone (**8**; 38 mg) were eluted with hexane-EtOAc (1 : 1) and hexane-EtOAc (2 : 3) respectively.

trans-Δ^{19,20}-20-*O*-Acetylmappicine (6) : M.p. 158–160° (Found : C, 72.79; H, 5.32; N, 7.97. C₂₁H₁₈N₂O₃ requires : C, 72.83; H, 5.20; N, 8.09%); [α]_D²⁵ ± 0° (c 0.1357, MeOH); ν_{max} (KBr) 1751, 1653, 1597, 1458 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 8.33 (1H, s, H-7), 8.21 (1H, dd, *J* 8.5 and 1.5 Hz, H-12), 7.90 (1H, dt, *J* 8.5 and 1.5 Hz, H-9), 7.81 (1H, dt, *J* 8.5 and 1.5 Hz, H-11), 7.62 (1H, dt, *J* 8.5 and 1.5 Hz, H-10), 7.26 (1H, s, H-14), 5.63 (1H, d, *J* 7.0 Hz, H-19), 5.28 (2H, br s, H₂-5), 2.36 (3H, s, Me-17), 2.22 (3H, s, OAc), 1.79 (1H, d, *J* 7.0 Hz, Me-18); *m/z* 346 (M⁺), 304, 289, 248, 219, 149.

cis-Δ^{19,20}-20-*O*-Acetylmappicine (7) : Viscous (Found : C, 72.68; H, 5.08; N, 8.12. C₂₁H₁₈N₂O₃ requires : C, 72.83; H, 5.20; N, 8.09%); [α]_D²⁵ ± 0° (c 0.1562, MeOH); ν_{max} (neat) 1750, 1652, 1590, 1455 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 8.30 (1H, s, H-7), 8.18 (1H, dd, *J* 8.5 and 1.5 Hz, H-12), 7.88 (1H, dd, *J* 8.5 and 1.5 Hz, H-9), 7.82 (1H, dt, *J* 8.5 and 1.5 Hz, H-11), 7.60 (1H, dt, *J* 8.5 and 1.5 Hz, H-10), 7.27 (1H, s, H-14), 5.67 (1H, d, *J* 7.0 Hz, H-19), 5.26 (2H, br s, H₂-5), 2.31 (3H, s, Me-17), 2.13 (1H, s, OAc), 1.65 (1H, d, *J* 7.0 Hz, Me-18); *m/z* 346 (M⁺), 304, 274, 289, 219.

17-Acetylmappicine ketone : Viscous (Found : C, 72.42; H, 5.24; N, 8.16. C₂₁H₁₈N₂O₃ requires : C, 72.83; H, 5.20; N, 8.09%); [α]_D²⁵ ± 0° (c 0.1286, MeOH); ν_{max} (neat) 1720, 1700, 1652, 1580, 1465 cm⁻¹; ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 8.26 (1H, s, H-7), 8.20 (1H, dd, *J* 8.5 and 1.5 Hz, H-12), 7.92 (1H, dd, *J* 8.5 and 1.5 Hz, H-9), 7.80 (1H, dt, *J* 8.5 and 1.5 Hz, H-11), 7.63 (1H, dt, *J* 8.5 and 1.5 Hz, H-10), 5.25 (2H, br s, H₂-5), 2.92 (2H, q, *J* 7.0 Hz, H₂-19), 2.23 (2H, s, H₂-17), 2.11 (3H, s, Ac), 1.28 (3H, d, *J* 7.0 Hz, Me-18); *m/z* 346 (M⁺), 331, 317, 303, 219.

Alkaline hydrolysis of trans-Δ^{19,20}-20-*O*-acetylmappicine (6) and cis-Δ^{19,20}-20-*O*-acetylmappicine (7) : *Trans*-Δ^{19,20}-20-*O*-acetylmappicine (**6**; 150 mg) was refluxed with 10% KOH in MeOH (50 ml) for 2 h. The mix-

ture was then cooled, diluted with water (50 ml) and MeOH removed under reduced pressure. The aqueous portion was neutralised with dilute HCl and extracted with EtOAc (3×50 ml). The extract was dried and concentrated. The residue was purified by column chromatography to afford mappicine ketone (**4**; 126 mg), m.p. 230–231°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} \pm 0^\circ$ (*c* 0.1525, MeOH); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1705, 1649, 1602, 1445 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (CDCl_3) 8.37 (1H, s, H-7), 8.18 (1H, dd, *J* 8.5 and 1.5 Hz, H-12), 7.91 (1H, dd, *J* 8.5 and 1.5 Hz, H-9), 7.82 (1H, dt, *J* 8.5 and 1.5 Hz, H-11), 7.63 (1H, dt, *J* 8.5 and 1.5 Hz, H-10), 7.22 (1H, s, H-14), 5.29 (2H, br s, H₂-5), 2.89 (2H, q, *J* 7.0 Hz, H₂-19), 2.30 (3H, s, Me-17), 1.28 (3H, t, *J* 7.0 Hz, Me-18); *m/z* 304 (M^+), 289, 248, 219, 191, 125. The structure of the product **4** was confirmed by direct comparison with an authentic sample of mappicine ketone⁸.

Cis- Δ^{20} -20-*O*-acetylmappicine (**7**; 50 mg) was also hydrolysed with 10% KOH in MeOH (20 ml) by following the above mentioned method to produce the similar product, mappicine ketone (**4**; 38 mg).

Reduction of mappicine ketone (4) with baker's yeast : Baker's yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) (2 g) was added to a vigorously stirred solution of sucrose (1.5 g) in tap water (200 ml). Phosphate buffer solution of pH 7.2 (20 ml) was added to the mixture. The suspension was stirred for 1 h at room temperature. Mappicine ketone (**4**; 100 mg) was added with constant stirring. Three portions of fermenting baker's yeast [1.5 g in a solution of sucrose (750 mg) in tap water (50 ml)] were added during 72 h and the mixture was stirred for another 120 h at room temperature. The suspension was extracted with EtOAc (3 × 100 ml). The extract was dried, concentrated and purified by column chromatography to yield (*S*)-mappicine (**5**; 75 mg), m.p. 250–251° (MeOH), $[\alpha]_D^{25} -10.62^\circ$ (*c* 0.1897, CHCl_3 -MeOH, 4 : 1); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3407, 1654, 1580 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (CDCl_3 - CD_3OD) 8.38 (1H, s, H-7), 8.12 (1H, dd, *J* 8.5 and 1.5 Hz, H-12), 7.88 (1H, dd, *J* 8.5 and 1.5 Hz, H-9), 7.77 (1H, dt, *J* 8.5 and 1.5 Hz, H-11), 7.63–7.54 (2H, m, H-10 and H-14), 5.23 (2H, br s, H₂-5), 4.86 (1H, t, *J* 6.5 Hz, H-20), 2.22 (3H, s, Me-17), 1.86–1.60 (2H, m, H₂-19), 1.03 (3H, t, *J* 7.0 Hz, Me-18); *m/z* 306 (M^+), 291, 277, 248, 219, 191, 167, 140. The structure of the product (**5**) was established by comparison of its physical and spectral properties with those reported in the literature⁹ and also by direct comparison with an authentic sample of naturally occurring (*S*)-mappicine, $[\alpha]_D^{25} -12.4^\circ$ (*c* 0.9135, CHCl_3 -MeOH, 4 : 1).

Oxidation of (*S*)-mappicine (5) with pyridinium chlorochromate (PCC) : (*S*)-Mappicine (20 mg) was taken in CH_2Cl_2 (5 ml) and stirred. PCC (30 mg) was added and the reaction mixture stirred overnight at room temperature. The mixture was filtered. The filtrate was concentrated and

purified by column chromatography to yield mappicine ketone (**4**; 14 mg), m.p. 230–231° (MeOH), $[\alpha]_D^{25} \pm 0^\circ$ (*c* 0.2017, MeOH). The spectral properties of the product were identical to those of the compound obtained from alkaline hydrolysis of *trans*- $\Delta^{19,20}$ -20-*O*-acetylmappicine (**6**). The product **4** was directly compared with an authentic sample of mappicine ketone⁸.

Baker's yeast treatment of *trans*- $\Delta^{19,20}$ -20-*O*-acetylmappicine (6) : *Trans*- $\Delta^{19,20}$ -20-*O*-acetylmappicine (**6**; 100 mg) was treated with baker's yeast following the method described above for the conversion of mappicine ketone (**3**) to (*S*)-mappicine (**4**). Tlc experiment showed the formation of two products. These were separated by column chromatography to give mappicine ketone (**4**; 58 mg), m.p. 231–232° (MeOH), $[\alpha]_D^{25} \pm 0^\circ$ (*c* 0.2157, MeOH) and (*S*)-mappicine (**5**; 21 mg), m.p. 250–251° (MeOH), $[\alpha]_D^{25} -10.64^\circ$ (*c* 0.1659, CHCl_3 -MeOH, 4 : 1). The spectral properties of **4** and **5** were similar to those discussed above for mappicine ketone and (*S*)-mappicine respectively. A direct comparison with the authentic samples^{8,9} confirmed the structures of the products.

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